

Innovation in Teaching Materials for Poetry Containing Local Wisdom On the Gift of the Sea

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ABSTRACT: This research was motivated by the need for more contextual and relevant poetry teaching materials for students, particularly in recognizing and describing local wisdom in the areas surrounding the students. The objective of this development research is to produce innovative poetry teaching materials containing local wisdom about sea offerings as the main learning resource, integrating the use of QR code scanning. The use of QR code scanning was chosen because of its speed, efficiency, and ease of accessing additional information (such as images, videos, or other information links related to the sea offering activity) without the need for manual typing. The research method used was Research and Development (R&D) with an adapted development model. The research stages included analyzing student needs, designing teaching materials, developing a prototype of teaching materials for poetry containing local wisdom on sea offerings, validation by subject matter experts and media experts, revisions based on expert input, small-scale trials with students, and analysis of limited trial results data. The expected outcome of this research is the creation of innovative, interactive, and effective poetry teaching materials that improve students' ability to write poetry. In addition, this teaching material is expected to foster students' pride and appreciation of the local wisdom of sedekah laut, as well as increase their motivation to learn through a more realistic and interesting learning experience. Thus, poetry learning does not only focus on theory, but also on students' direct experience in observing and describing the local wisdom of sedekah laut in their surrounding areas.

KEYWORDS: Innovation, Poetry, Local wisdom, Sea almsgiving.

INTRODUCTION

Learning is a teaching and learning process that involves interaction between teachers and students. Learning includes components such as teachers, students, teaching materials, content, learning media, and evaluation. If one of the components in learning is lacking or missing, learning will not run smoothly. In essence, learning must be continuous between one learning component and another. Based on this learning experience, various learning methods and strategies have been developed.

One indicator of successful learning is when teachers are able to design teaching materials that are tailored to the characteristics of students, their needs, and the achievement of learning objectives. Teachers need to be innovative in communicating the knowledge they will convey through teaching materials in order to improve the quality of the learning process (Jannah, M., et al., 2022).

The learning process cannot be separated from the teaching materials and learning materials used. Learning materials play an important role in learning activities. One example of learning material is poetry in the Merdeka Curriculum Learning Outcomes for Indonesian Language Phase D (for grades VII, VIII, IX of junior high school/MTs/Program Paket B), including the elements of listening, reading and viewing, speaking and presenting, and writing. In accordance with the independent curriculum standards, eighth-grade students are expected to be able to create poetry. By learning poetry, students can understand prismatic poetry, the elements of poetry, how to write poetry, and how to recite it.

A teacher cannot explain the material on free verse poetry in its entirety without teaching materials. Teaching materials are very helpful in learning activities so that the material is better conveyed. The availability of teaching materials also makes students more interested in learning the material taught by the teacher. The teaching materials used by teachers are very helpful for students in learning a complete set of competencies so that students are able to master the entire content of poetry writing in a way that is easy to understand. (Irwanti, E, 2017).

Teaching materials, as one component of learning, can determine the success of the learning process objectives set by the

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government. The use of good teaching materials will improve student learning outcomes and make it easier for students to understand what is being taught. Therefore, teaching materials are very important and needed by teachers to support learning and improve interactive and effective learning processes. Learning with teaching materials that are systematically organized and in line with the current curriculum will make it easier for teachers to explain the material and achieve the specified competencies. However, the development of teaching materials is not yet accurate, especially in Indonesian language subjects, namely poetry.

Based on observations and interviews with several Indonesian language teachers at junior high schools in Rembang Regency, it appears that teaching materials for poetry at the junior high school/MTs level are currently unavailable or rarely found in some schools and among students. In addition, many students still experience difficulties, resulting in outcomes that fall short of expectations. This is evident in the low scores achieved by students in poetry lessons. The average test scores for one of the topics covered in poetry are still below the Learning Objective Achievement Criteria (KKTP). The difficulties experienced by students include not being able to: express ideas or thoughts, choose the right words (diction), determine the values contained in poetry, and recite poetry. The poetry material contained in the learning resources also does not discuss local wisdom in their environment.

Efforts that can be made to improve students' competence in poetry include developing teaching materials that can assist students in the learning process, understanding, or helping to develop students' knowledge potential broadly. One way to develop such teaching materials is to develop teaching materials that incorporate local wisdom. The development of teaching materials that incorporate local wisdom is a process of developing teaching materials that can be used as guidelines or for teaching by utilizing the circumstances found in the students' environment as a supplement to learning. The application of local wisdom is related to the dimension of the Pancasila student profile, namely global diversity, which teaches the importance of preserving noble culture, locality, and Indonesian identity while remaining open-minded in interacting with other cultures.

Local wisdom in certain areas is unique and only practiced by certain communities. The value of local wisdom has a distinctiveness that is inherent to a particular area and is applied in everyday life. One activity that is easy to implement local wisdom values is through learning in schools. The application of local wisdom values in learning aims to preserve the local culture of a particular region, as students can easily understand the material and it helps them to develop their potential and abilities.

The application of local wisdom values through the development of poetry teaching materials is an activity aimed at fulfilling teaching materials that have not been provided optimally. The development of poetry teaching materials is also carried out to meet the needs and characteristics of students in accordance with the applicable curriculum. Therefore, the development of poetry teaching materials is carried out to solve existing problems and provide learning materials for students that are easier for them to understand. The provision of teaching materials is also a requirement for teachers in supporting their profession in the world of education.

The provision of teaching materials is used as needed for students, independent sources of materials, in accordance with learning objectives, learning outcomes, or the applicable curriculum. The development of these poetry teaching materials aims to overcome the problems faced, so poetry teaching materials containing local wisdom are developed for use in school learning. The problem faced is the difficulty of finding teaching materials or content that are appropriate for the surrounding environment.

Based on this background, the research question in this article is: What are the requirements for developing teaching materials for poetry containing local wisdom on sea offerings for eighth-grade junior high school students in Rembang Regency? The objective is to describe the initial requirements for developing teaching materials for poetry containing local wisdom on sea offerings for eighth-grade junior high school students in Rembang Regency.

1. Teaching Materials

According to Pannin (in Prastowo, 2015), teaching materials are materials or lesson materials that are systematically arranged and used by teachers and students in the learning process in the classroom. Teaching materials are learning materials, both written and unwritten, that are systematically arranged to assist teachers and students in the learning process in order to achieve the specified competency standards. The development of teaching materials is the activity of designing learning materials into materials that are ready to be delivered or used in the learning process.

2. Poetry

Poetry is a literary work that has high aesthetic (artistic) value and originates from the interpretation of human life experiences that are composed in the most memorable form or as a result of the poet's imagination and ideas that are expressed in a specific typographical form (Wicaksono, 2014). Wahyudi and Doyin (2015) explain that poetry is a distinctive form of language, containing experiences that are arranged in a distinctive way, as well as the inner experiences contained in poetry, which are arranged from what has been given meaning and interpreted aesthetically.

3. Local Wisdom

Local wisdom is an important part of the culture of the surrounding community that shapes activities and traditions. Local wisdom is the intelligence possessed by certain ethnic groups that is acquired through community experience. Local wisdom can help students acquire competencies that are useful for global competition (Rahyono, 2009).

4. Tradion of Sea Alms

Tradition is a legacy passed down from previous generations or ancestors in the form of symbols, materials, objects, policies, and principles (Rofiq, 2019). Hapsari et al. (2023) reveal that tradition is one of the valuable assets that form the identity of a nation because Indonesia is rich in cultural diversity. Sedekah laut is one of the nation's cultures or traditions that has values that can be learned and preserved, especially for the younger generation.

Several previous studies relevant to this study are described as follows. A study on the tradition of sea almsgiving conducted by (Widati., 2011). The purpose of this study was to explain and describe changes in the form of sea almsgiving, changes in the function of sea almsgiving, and the role of sea almsgiving in education for the community. The results and discussion of the study show that the tradition of sea almsgiving has undergone changes in form and function due to socio-cultural changes in the Wonokerto community, including changes in the scientific system, economic system, and technology. The relevance of this study to the present study is that both discuss the tradition of sea almsgiving. The difference is that this study was conducted to develop teaching materials containing local wisdom on sea offerings, while the aforementioned study examined changes in the form and function of sea offerings.

The study (Abdurrohman., 2015) aims to provide a clearer picture of one of the cultures in Central Java, namely the culture of sedekah laut (sea alms), and invites readers to understand the symbols contained in the traditional sedekah laut ceremony in Tanjungan Village, Kragan District, Rembang Regency as a communication phenomenon that shapes a culture. The relevance of this research to the present study is that both discuss the sea offering in Rembang Regency. The difference is that the former discusses understanding the symbolic meanings in the traditional sea offering ceremony in Rembang Regency, while the latter develops teaching materials for poetry.

Another study (Harahap et al., 2023) on the development of poetry teaching materials based on the picture and picture model concluded that the design of poetry teaching materials based on the picture and picture model was good and successful. The teaching materials and media/tools applied by the researchers to students made it easier for them to express their ideas in writing poetry. The relevance to this study is that both studies developed poetry teaching materials. The difference lies in the formal object; the formal object of that study was the picture and picture model, while the formal object of this study was the local wisdom of sea alms.

This study discusses the dynamics and adaptation of the sea offering tradition in Muarareja, which is an annual ritual of the fishing community. The relevance to this study is that both studies conduct research on sea offerings. The difference is that the study discusses the dynamics and adaptation of the sea offering tradition in Muarareja, while this study is about the development of poetry teaching materials.

(Monica et al., 2024) conducted research on the development of teaching materials for folk poetry based on the local wisdom of the Deli Malay. The study aimed to develop teaching materials in the form of learning modules for folk poetry based on the local wisdom of the Deli Malay and to test the feasibility of the developed product. The similarity between the two studies lies in their discussion of poetry based on local wisdom. The difference between the two studies is that the former limited the type of poetry to folk poetry based on the local wisdom of the Deli Malay, while the latter used any type of poetry containing the local wisdom of the sea offerings of Rembang Regency.

METHOD

This study uses the research and development (R&D) method. The research and development method is a method used to produce certain products and test their effectiveness (Sugiyono, 2016). The main objective of this study is to develop effective products for use in schools. To produce a specific product, a needs analysis study (using survey or qualitative methods) was conducted, and to test the effectiveness of the product (using experimental methods). The research was carried out in five stages designed in accordance with the ten stages of development from Borg and Gall. The following are the stages that were carried out.

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The data sources for this study were expert lecturers who served as examiners and advisors on media and learning drafts, two Indonesian language teachers from Kragan 4 Satu Atap Public Junior High School and Sluke 1 Public Junior High School, and students from both schools for needs analysis and limited testing, consisting of two classes with 48 students.

The data collection techniques used were tests and non-tests in the form of observations, questionnaires, and interviews. Observations were made by observing the learning process. The research questionnaires consisted of a needs questionnaire and a validation questionnaire. The needs questionnaire was given to teachers and eighth-grade students in two different schools. The validation questionnaire was used to obtain valid scores for the prototype poetry teaching materials for eighth-grade students. The validation questionnaire was filled out by experts in teaching material development. In addition, interviews were also conducted with respondents. The interviews were conducted to find out the responses, comments, and suggestions of teachers and students after using the poetry teaching materials containing local wisdom about sea offerings. The test technique was used at the end of the learning process to determine the learning outcomes using the poetry teaching materials containing local wisdom about sea offerings.

The technique used in the data analysis of this study was descriptive qualitative. Numerical data was analyzed and then described. Descriptive qualitative analysis was used to analyze the results of interviews, questionnaires, and observations. Quantitative analysis was used to analyze data obtained from test results.

RESULTS

Based on observations, interviews, and questionnaire analysis on the availability of poetry teaching materials, it was found that both SMP Negeri 4 Satu Atap Kragan and SMP Negeri 1 Sluke already have teaching materials that include poetry, namely the Indonesian Language textbook for Grade VIII published by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in 2016, while teaching materials specifically discussing poetry are not yet available. In addition to using textbooks, poetry teaching materials are also obtained from other sources, including the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the internet, and 75% of the LKPD. Based on the results of the analysis of the questionnaire on the needs of teachers and students, it was found that both teachers and students stated that they needed teaching materials on poetry that included content such as the definition of poetry, elements of poetry, examples of poetry, and practice questions. The preferred question formats were multiple choice and essay questions.

The physical appearance desired by teachers is a colored cover with attractive illustrations. Based on an analysis of the needs of educators and students, the desired book size is B5 with a font size of 12. After analyzing the needs of students and teachers and drafting the teaching materials, the next step is to validate the draft teaching materials. This validation is intended to obtain suggestions and input on the draft teaching materials to be developed. The teaching material feasibility test produced two types of data, namely quantitative and qualitative data. The questionnaire instrument used produced quantitative data containing numbers from a set of assessment items. The instrument covered several aspects, including: presentation of material, material, language and readability, graphics, and suggestions for improving the development of teaching materials.

DISCUSSION

The teaching materials on poetry used in schools are taken from the Indonesian language textbook for junior high school/MTs Grade VIII published by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in 2016. Teaching materials specifically discussing poetry are not yet widely available. In addition to textbooks, students and teachers obtain information about poetry from student workbooks. Teaching materials that discuss poetry are needed by educators and students. This is to assist learning activities and improve students' poetry skills.

The teaching material required is a B5-sized module book with a cover that matches the illustration described. The desired

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content includes the definition of poetry, elements of poetry, examples of poetry, and practice questions.

CONCLUSION

This study is expected to produce poetry teaching materials containing local wisdom for eighth-grade students in Rembang Regency. The teaching materials produced are in line with the needs of teachers and students. Based on the results of the study, several suggestions can be made, including:

1. The teaching materials in this study can be used as alternative poetry materials for eighth grade students in Rembang Regency.
2. Considering that the research products can benefit learning, it is recommended that teachers develop these products with a broader scope.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Abdurrohman, M. 2015. "Memahami Makna-makna Simbolik pada Upacara Adat Sedekah Laut di Desa Tanjung Kecamatan Kragan Kabupaten Rembang". *Jurnal The Messenger*, (online), volume VII, Nomor 1, (<https://journals.usm.ac.id/index.php/the-messenger/article/view/286>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).
- 2) Amanatin, E.L., dkk. 2024. "Ritus Sedekah Laut sebagai Mekanisme Sosial Masyarakat Nelayan Urban di Muarareja Kota Tegal". *Jayapangus Press Ganaya : Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Humaniora*, (online), Volume 7, Nomor 3, (<https://doi.org/10.37329/ganaya.v7i3.3376>, diakses 17 Oktober 2025).
- 3) Hapsari, C.R., dkk. 2023. "Nilai Budaya dalam Tradisi Sedekah Laut Desa Bendar, Juwana, Pati". *PESHUM: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial dan Humaniora*, (online), vol.2, No.5, (<https://journal-nusantara.com/index.php/PESHUM/article/view/2241>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).
- 4) Harahap, R. & Nurapriana. 2023. "Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Puisi Berbasis Model *Picture and Picture* pada Siswa Kelas VIII SMP Al-Razi Sinar Harapan Tahun Pelajaran 2022-2023". *JP2BS: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra*, (online), vol. 8, No. 1, (<https://jurnal-lp2m.um naw.ac.id/index.php/JP2BS/article/view/2054>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).
- 5) Irwanti, E. 2017. "Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Menulis Puisi Bebas Kelas VIII SMP Xaverius Tugumulyo". *Jurnal KIBASP (Kajian, Bahasa, Sastra dan Pengajaran)*, (online), Volume 1, Nomor 1, (<https://doi.org/10.31539/kibasp.v1i1.105>, diakses 14 Oktober 2024).
- 6) Jannah, M., dkk. 2022. "Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Modul Menulis Puisi Berbasis Pendekatan Saintifik untuk siswa Kelas VIII SMPN 5 Kota Bengkulu". *Jurnal Pustaka Indonesia*, (online), Vol. 2, No. 3, (<https://doi.org/10.62159/jpi.v2i1.422>, diakses 12 Oktober 2024).
- 7) Monica, S.M., dkk. 2024. "Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Puisi Rakyat Berbasis Kearifan Lokal Melayu Deli pada Siswa Kelas VII SMP Tahun Pelajaran 2023-2024". *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, (online), volume 8, Nomor 1, (<https://jptam.org/index.php/jptam/article/view/14410>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).
- 8) Prastowo, A. 2015. *Panduan Kreatif Membuat Bahan Ajar Inovatif*. Yogyakarta: Diva Press.
- 9) Rofiq, A. 2019. "Tradisi Slametan Jawa dalam Perspektif Pendidikan Islam". *ATTAQWA: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Islam*, (online), vol. 15, No. 2, (<https://jurnal.insida.ac.id/index.php/attaqwa/article/view/13>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).
- 10) Rahyono, F.X. 2009. *Kearifan Budaya dalam Kata*. Jakarta: Wedatama Widya Sastra.
- 11) Sugiyono. 2016. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 12) Wahyudi, F.A. & Doyin, M. 2015. "Pengembangan Buku Pop Up Tiga Dimensi sebagai Media Pembelajaran Menulis Puisi". *Jurnal Lingua*, (online), vol. 11, No. 2, (<https://journal.unnes.ac.id/nju/lingua/article/view/8764>, diakses 25 Juni 2024).
- 13) Wicaksono, Andri. 2014. *Menulis Kreatif Sastra dan Beberapa Model Pembelajarannya*. Yogyakarta: Garudhawaca.
- 14) Widati, S. 2011. "Tradisi Sedekah Laut di Wonokerto Kabupaten Pekalongan: Kajian Perubahan Bentuk dan Fungsi". *JPP, Program Pascasarjana, Kampus Unnes Bendan Ngisor, Universitas Negeri Semarang*, (online), vol. 1, No. 2, (<https://journal.unnes.ac.id/nju/jppasca/article/view/1538>, diakses 24 Juni 2024).